

GLOBAL VALUE CHAINS PARTICIPATION AND EMPLOYMENT CREATION IN NIGERIA'S MANUFACTURING SECTOR: KEY DETERMINANTS AND OUTCOMES

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ABSTRACT

This study explores how Global Value Chain (GVC) participation influences employment in Nigeria's manufacturing sector, using 1981–2024 data and an ARDL framework. Global Value Chain and Human Capital theories guide the analysis, with manufacturing value-added and intermediate goods imports as proxies for GVC. Results show a positive short-run relationship between manufacturing value-added and employment, while intermediate goods imports have no significant effect. Labour cost negatively impacts employment in the long run, and skills development consistently supports job creation. Exchange rate and foreign direct investment effects vary by context, while government expenditure shows a long-run negative impact on employment. The study concludes that GVC participation through domestic value addition supports employment, but maximising gains requires investment in skills development, labour reforms, and efficient government spending to enhance local production and strengthen employment outcomes.

Keywords: Employment; Foreign direct investment; Global value chains; Human capital; Labour costs; Manufacturing; Nigeria; Value-added.

JEL Codes: F23, J21.

I. INTRODUCTION

Global Value Chains (GVCs) have become a defining feature of contemporary trade, enabling firms worldwide to organise production across multiple countries, leveraging each location's comparative advantages to drive efficiency and growth. By specialising in specific stages of production rather than full product creation, GVCs enable countries to focus on sectors where they hold competitive advantages, potentially fostering economic growth and employment (Gereffi & Lee, 2016). For developing economies, particularly those in sub-Saharan Africa, GVC integration offers a pathway to industrialisation and job creation, promising to improve employment prospects in sectors like manufacturing (World Bank, 2020).

Yet, despite these potential benefits, the impact of GVC participation on employment remains debated, particularly in Nigeria's manufacturing sector, where empirical findings are often inconsistent. Insights from local value chains, however, provide useful guidance on employment dynamics. For instance, Oni, Ojekunle, Irinyemi, and Alaba (2023) show that a firm's location relative to transport infrastructure significantly influences manufacturing supply chain performance, with direct implications for labour utilisation. Similarly, participation in agricultural and rural processing value chains has been shown to generate employment across multiple stages of production and marketing (Musa, 2021; Oladele,

Ayomide, & Oladoyin, 2026). In addition, Anyanwu, Uwazie, and Mbakwe (2025) emphasise that strategies promoting export diversification and value chain development can foster broader economic growth, while engagement in non-farm value chains improves rural incomes and employment (Nnadi, Ossai, Akukwe, & Chiatula, 2024). Although derived from local chains, these findings collectively suggest that effective integration into GVCs could similarly support job creation within Nigeria's manufacturing sector.

Recent studies on GVC-related employment effects in Nigeria offer contrasting perspectives. For instance, Uesugi and Afolayan (2023) provide evidence of positive employment impacts from GVC participation, suggesting that enhanced integration creates opportunities for labour-intensive manufacturing activities. In contrast, Pahl and Timmer (2019) report no discernible employment effect, indicating that Nigeria's involvement in GVCs may not inherently lead to job creation. These mixed results highlight a significant gap in understanding the specific conditions under which GVC participation translates into meaningful employment outcomes within Nigeria's manufacturing sector.

This research aims to address this gap by examining the conditions under which GVC participation influences employment outcomes in Nigeria's manufacturing sector. Specifically, this study will analyse factors such as skill requirements, labour costs, and macroeconomic factors to determine how GVC integration impacts job creation in the manufacturing sector. By identifying the key determinants of employment within Nigeria's GVC-participating manufacturing sector, this study will provide insights that could help policymakers and business leaders leverage GVCs for more inclusive and sustainable industrial growth. Such insights will contribute to the literature by clarifying how GVC participation can support employment in Nigeria, thus filling a critical empirical gap and informing strategies for maximising the potential of GVCs in the manufacturing sector. Therefore, the objective of this study is to investigate the specific conditions that influence employment outcomes resulting from Nigeria's participation in Global Value Chains (GVCs) within its manufacturing sector.

2. LITRATURE REVIEW

2.1 Conceptual Review

Global Value Chains (GVCs) enable countries to participate in specific production stages, allowing specialisation and integration into international trade without producing complete goods (Gereffi & Lee, 2016). This can enhance competitiveness and generate employment, especially in labour-intensive industries, though effects vary by sector and level of economic development (World Bank, 2020; OECD, 2018). GVCs create both direct and indirect jobs by increasing demand for intermediate and final products, but the magnitude depends on domestic capabilities and industrial structure.

Employment outcomes within GVCs are closely linked to skill requirements. Higher skill levels improve competitiveness and create higher-quality jobs in sectors demanding skilled labour (Taglioni & Winkler, 2016). In contrast, economies reliant on unskilled labour may see limited benefits, as low-skill jobs are often outsourced or automated (OECD, 2018). Thus, investment in education and vocational training is essential for maximising employment gains. Labour costs further influence GVC participation and job creation. Competitive wages attract foreign investment to cost-effective production locations, but excessively low wages may undermine living standards and limit employment benefits (UNCTAD, 2020; ILO, 2021). Therefore, a balanced labour cost structure is necessary to optimise the employment potential of GVC integration.

Overall, the interplay of domestic value addition, skills, and labour costs determines the extent to which GVC engagement translates into meaningful employment in the manufacturing sector.

2.2. Theoretical Literature

This study is built on the Global Value Chain and Human Capital theories. The Global Value Chain (GVC) theory, developed by Gereffi (1994), posits that production processes are increasingly organised across borders, allowing firms and countries to specialise in specific segments of the value chain. This specialisation can lead to improved efficiency and competitiveness, which is particularly significant for developing countries like Nigeria. GVC theory emphasises that participation in global networks can enhance local industries by providing access to international markets, technology transfer, and better management practices (Gereffi & Fernandez-Stark, 2016). In the context of employment creation, GVC participation can lead to both direct job creation in manufacturing and indirect employment opportunities in related sectors. Understanding how Nigeria's manufacturing sector can engage effectively in GVCs is essential for maximising employment outcomes.

The Human Capital theory, articulated by Becker (1993), argues that investments in education and training increase an individual's productivity and, consequently, their potential earnings. This theory is critical in understanding the relationship between skill requirements and employment outcomes in the GVC context. In Nigeria's manufacturing sector, the ability to meet the skill demands of GVCs can significantly influence the quality and quantity of jobs created. Higher levels of human capital enable workers to engage in more complex production processes, increasing their employability and the overall efficiency of the sector (Leoni, 2023). Thus, as Nigeria integrates more deeply into GVCs, enhancing the skill levels of the workforce becomes crucial for maximising employment benefits and supporting economic growth.

2.3. Empirical Literature

Studies examining GVC participation's role in employment generation provide insights into its positive effects on the industrial and manufacturing sectors. Uesugi and Afolayan (2023) used multivariate analysis to investigate the impact of GVC on employment and economic growth in small and medium-scale enterprises (SMEs) in Lagos, Nigeria. The correlation test results identified SMEs as drivers of employment creation and economic growth. Similarly, Oladapo and Rafiu (2022) evaluated the relationship between GVC participation and employment within Nigeria's industrial sector, analysing quarterly data from 1991 to 2015. The findings, based on Dynamic Ordinary Least Squares, revealed a positive relationship between backward GVC participation and total employment, benefiting the industrial sector through various linkages. Despite the general trend, Pahl and Timmer (2019) found no significant evidence linking GVC participation to employment generation in developing countries. The study assessed 58 countries' formal manufacturing sectors and discovered that while GVC contributed to productivity growth, this did not necessarily translate into employment generation.

GVC participation also influences business investment, particularly through its impact on capital and business culture. Chukwukadiba et al. (2023) investigated globalisation's effect on business investment in Nigeria's South East region, utilising questionnaires. The results from the t-tests revealed that foreign direct investment (FDI) significantly influenced manufacturing industries' working capital. Furthermore, the study noted that GVCs shaped business investment culture, demonstrating the intertwined role of globalisation and GVC in investment behaviours and capital utilisation in Nigeria. Agostino et al. (2019) contributed to this theme by focusing on GVC and firm efficiency in Italy. Using descriptive statistics and Data Envelopment Analysis (DEA), the authors observed that firms actively participating in GVCs, especially as suppliers, exhibited higher levels of technical efficiency. This finding underscores GVC's role in promoting efficiency and investment in supplier roles within industrial value chains.

Backward and forward linkages within GVCs form another significant theme in GVC research, with implications for productivity and export growth. Olasehinde-Williams and Oshodi (2021) explored GVC and export growth in South Africa, applying a dynamic ARDL model over a period from 1990 to 2019. The study revealed that backward linkages, or foreign value-added, significantly affected long-term export growth, while forward linkages, or indirect value-added, impacted short-term growth. Similarly, Zhang, Liu, and Huang (2020) analysed China's equipment manufacturing exports from 2004 to 2014. The panel regression indicated that embedded GVCs, both backward and forward, promoted industrial exports, with backward GVCs yielding stronger effects. Kouton and Amonie (2020) also observed in an ARDL analysis of 35 African countries, including Nigeria, that backward linkages improved labour productivity, while forward linkages yielded positive impacts on productivity in the short term. The impact of GVC participation on productivity is emphasised in studies that highlight GVC's role in promoting efficiency, technical advancement, and industry competitiveness. Pahl and Timmer (2019) identified a robust, positive relationship between GVC participation and productivity growth in formal manufacturing sectors across 58 countries. The research found that productivity gains from GVCs were amplified as the gap with the global productivity frontier widened. This suggests that developing countries may particularly benefit from GVCs as they close productivity gaps with more advanced economies. Banga (2019) examined the role of digitalisation within GVCs and found it to be a significant driver of upgrading to higher value-added activities in India's manufacturing sector. Utilising the General Method of Moments (GMM) approach on data from 2001 to 2015, the study demonstrated that increased digital capabilities positively influenced firms' product sophistication. Factors such as industry concentration, size, and R&D investment were also found to enhance product sophistication within GVCs.

Another critical dimension of GVC participation relates to environmental impact and technology. Ye, Shi, and Sun (2019) used systematic GMM and quantile regression on U.S. multinational industry data to study the relationship between the technology gap and carbon intensity from 1970 to 2010. The result suggested that narrowing the technology gap reduced carbon intensity, and that GVC positioning influenced this relationship. This study highlights the role of technological advancement within GVCs in minimising environmental impacts and enhancing sustainable practices.

3. METHODOLOGY AND DATA

3.1. Model Specification

This study focuses on understanding the relationship between global value chains (GVCs) participation and employment creation in Nigeria's manufacturing sector. Given the mixed orders of integration of the variables, the ARDL model is suitable for capturing both short-term and long-term relationships. In an ARDL framework, the dependent variable (manufacturing employment) is regressed on its own lagged values and the lagged values of the independent variables: manufacturing value added, labour cost, skills requirement, GDP growth, exchange rate, foreign direct investment, inflation, and government expenditure. To account for GVC participation, this study uses manufacturing value added as a proxy. These variables capture key macroeconomic and sectoral dynamics influencing employment in the manufacturing sector.

Based on the institutional knowledge of the Nigerian economy, the basic ARDL model for the study can be specified as follows:

$$\begin{aligned}
 EMP_t = & \alpha_0 + \sum_{j=1}^p \alpha_j EMP_{t-j} + \sum_{j=0}^{q1} \beta_{1,t-j} MVA + \sum_{j=0}^{q2} \beta_{2,t-j} LAB + \sum_{j=0}^{q3} \beta_{3,t-j} SKI \\
 & + \sum_{j=0}^{q4} \beta_{4,t-j} GDP + \sum_{j=0}^{q5} \beta_{5,t-j} EXR \\
 & + \sum_{j=0}^{q6} \beta_{6,t-j} FDI + \sum_{j=0}^{q7} \beta_{7,t-j} INF + \sum_{j=0}^{q8} \beta_{8,t-j} GEX + \varepsilon_t \dots \dots \dots [1]
 \end{aligned}$$

Where EMP_t is the employment rate in manufacturing sector at time t, MVA = manufacturing value added, LAB = Labour cost (average wage in manufacturing sector) SKI= skill requirement (average education level of manufacturing workers), GDP= GDP growth, EXR=exchange rate, FDI=foreign direct investment, INF=inflation, and GEX= government expenditure. The a priori theoretical expectations from [1] are presented in Table 1.

Table 1: Theoretical Expectations of Variables

Variable	Coefficient	Expected Sign	Theoretical Justification
MVA	β_1	>0	Higher manufacturing output increases production and jobs.
LAB	β_2	<0	Higher labour costs reduce hiring or induce labour-saving tech.
SKI	β_3	>0	Skilled labour improves productivity and attracts investment.
GDP	β_4	>0	Economic growth boosts demand, production, and employment.
EXR	β_5	>0 / <0	Depreciation may increase export jobs but raise import costs.
FDI	β_6	>0	FDI provides capital, expanding production and jobs.
INF	β_7	<0	High inflation reduces demand, lowering production and employment.
GEX	β_8	>0	Government spending on infrastructure, industry support, and workforce development boosts productivity and employment.

Source: Authors' Own Compilation.

According to Pesaran et al. (2001), when cointegration is established, the standard ARDL model can be restructured into an Error Correction Model (ECM). This transformation enables the analysis of both short-term dynamics and long-term relationships, as demonstrated below:

$$\begin{aligned}
 EMP_t = & \alpha_0 + \sum_{j=1}^p \alpha_j \Delta EMP_{t-j} + \sum_{j=0}^{q_1} \beta_{1,j} \Delta MVA_{t-j} + \sum_{j=0}^{q_2} \beta_{2,j} \Delta LAB_{t-j} + \sum_{j=0}^{q_3} \beta_{3,j} \Delta SKI_{t-j} \\
 & + \sum_{j=0}^{q_4} \beta_{4,j} \Delta GDP_{t-j} + \sum_{j=0}^{q_5} \beta_{5,j} \Delta EXR_{t-j} + \sum_{j=0}^{q_6} \beta_{6,j} \Delta FDI_{t-j} + \sum_{j=0}^{q_7} \beta_{7,j} \Delta INF_{t-j} \\
 & + \sum_{j=0}^{q_8} \beta_{8,j} \Delta GEX_{t-j} + \theta_1 EMP_{t-1} + \theta_2 MVA_{t-1} + \theta_3 LAB_{t-1} + \theta_4 SKI_{t-1} \\
 & + \theta_5 GDP_{t-1} + \theta_6 EXR_{t-1} + \theta_7 FDI_{t-1} + \theta_8 INF_{t-1} + \theta_9 GEX_{t-1} \\
 & + \lambda ECM + \varepsilon_t \dots \dots \dots [2]
 \end{aligned}$$

Where $XEMP_t$ is the employment rate in manufacturing sector at time t, while α_0 is the constant term. The coefficients α_j correspond to the lagged dependent variable, EMP_{t-j} up to lag p. The terms $\beta_{1,j}$ to $\beta_{8,j}$ are the coefficients of the lagged explanatory variables, and $q_1 - q_8$ denote the optimal lags for these explanatory variables. The parameters α_j , and $\beta_1 - \beta_8$ represent the short-run coefficients, while θ_1 to θ_9 capture the long-run coefficients. The error term is denoted by ε_t . Once the ARDL model is estimated, an ECM can be derived if cointegration is confirmed. The ECM term indicates the speed at which deviations from the long-run equilibrium are corrected in subsequent periods.

The Global Value Chain theory suggests that Nigeria’s manufacturing sector can boost employment by specialising in segments of global production, gaining access to international markets, and adopting advanced technologies, while Human Capital theory highlights that developing workforce skills is essential to meet the demands of these global chains and enhance job quality and productivity. The dynamics of this interaction have been analysed through the ARDL model framework.

3.2. Procedure for estimation

To estimate the ARDL model, the Augmented Dickey-Fuller (ADF) and the Kwiatkowski-Phillips-Schmidt-Shin (KPSS) tests were used to conduct unit root and stationarity tests. The optimal lag length for each variable using AIC or SIC to balance model fit with complexity was determined. Tests for the existence of a long-term relationship using the bounds testing approach were implemented. If the F-statistic exceeded the upper critical value, cointegration was confirmed. Once cointegration was confirmed, the long-run coefficients $\theta_1 - \theta_9$ and the short-run coefficients $\beta_1 - \beta_8$ were estimated. Diagnostic tests (Ramsey Reset, serial correlation, heteroscedasticity, and normality tests) were then performed to ensure the validity of the model.

3.3. Data

This study employs annual data covering the period 1981–2024. Annual frequency is preferred because the determinants and outcomes of Global Value Chain (GVC) participation and employment reflect long-term structural and policy-driven dynamics rather than short-term cyclical movements. Using monthly or quarterly data could introduce distortions arising from seasonal patterns, temporary macroeconomic shocks, or short-lived policy adjustments. Annual data therefore help smooth such volatility and provide a clearer assessment of sustained trends in manufacturing employment and GVC integration. The starting year, 1981, corresponds with Nigeria’s structural adjustment reforms, which significantly altered industrial and trade policies and influenced GVC participation, while 2024 represents the most recent available data.

Manufacturing employment (EMP) is the dependent variable. The key explanatory variables include manufacturing value added (MVA) and intermediate goods imports (IMP) as proxies for GVC participation, as well as skill requirements (SKI) and labour cost (LAB). Exchange rate and inflation capture macroeconomic stability, while GDP growth rate, foreign direct investment (FDI) inflows, and government expenditure (GEX) serve as control variables. The kinds and sources of data are presented in Table 2.

Table 2: Kinds and Sources of Data

S/ No	Variable	Symbol	Unit / Measurement	Source
1	Employment	EMP	Manufacturing employment (% of total)	World Bank
2	Manufacturing Value Added	MVA	Natural log	World Bank
3	Intermediate Goods Imports	IMP	Value of imported parts/components (natural log)	World Bank
4	Labour Cost	LAB	Average wage in manufacturing (% of total employment)	World Bank
5	Skill Requirement	SKI	Average education level of manufacturing workers (completed secondary % of total)	World Bank
6	Gross Domestic Product	GDP	Nominal GDP growth rate (%)	World Bank
7	Exchange Rate	EXR	Naira/dollar (natural log)	World Bank
8	Foreign Direct Investment	FDI	FDI inflows (% of GDP)	World Bank
9	Inflation	INF	Consumer Price Index (%)	World Bank

Source: Authors' Own Compilation.

4. RESULTS AND INTERPRETATION

4.1. Descriptive statistics

Table 3 presents the descriptive properties of the study variables. The average employment rate (EMP) is 12.08, reflecting a moderate employment level, while manufacturing value-added (MVA) averages 29.15, indicating its contribution to the economy. Mean import value (IMP) is 24.23, labour cost (LAB) 16.94, and skill requirement (SKI) 39.98, showing variation in skill intensity across the period. GDP growth averages 5.05%, and foreign direct investment (FDI) is 20.19, highlighting average foreign investment inflows.

EMP ranges from 10.14 to 14.56, showing moderate variability, whereas MVA is relatively stable (28.72–29.54). FDI is highly volatile, ranging from -19.05 to 22.90, reflecting both inflows and periods of capital flight. Standard deviations indicate that FDI, SKI, and inflation are the most dynamic variables, while EMP (0.49) and GDP growth (0.43) show moderate positive skewness. FDI exhibits strong negative skewness (-4.53), suggesting frequent extreme negative values.

The Jarque-Bera test shows that most variables, including EMP, MVA, IMP, LAB, SKI, GDP growth, exchange rate (EXR), and inflation (INF) are normally distributed at the 5% level, while FDI is not. Non-normality in macroeconomic indicators like FDI is common and does not compromise analysis if other diagnostics (e.g., multicollinearity, heteroscedasticity, autocorrelation) are satisfied.

Table 3: Descriptive Statistics

Statistic	EMP	MVA	IMP	LAB	SKI	GDP	EXR	FDI	INF	GEX
Mean	12.08	29.15	24.23	16.94	39.98	5.05	5.24	20.19	13.12	8.27
Maximum	14.56	29.54	24.91	18.84	54.88	15.32	6.45	22.90	24.65	9.89

Minimum	10.14	28.72	22.88	14.00	24.74	-1.79	4.62	-19.05	5.38	6.55
Std. Dev.	1.42	0.33	0.61	1.78	7.47	3.63	0.50	8.38	4.46	0.90
Skewness	0.49	-0.00	-0.85	-0.70	-0.29	0.43	0.83	-4.53	0.49	-0.16
Jarque-Bera	1.95	3.35	3.21	3.29	0.74	2.39	3.01	434.00	1.02	0.72
Probability	0.37	0.18	0.20	0.19	0.69	0.30	0.22	0.00	0.59	0.69

Source: Authors' Computations.

4.2. Pre-estimation test

To assess the stationarity properties of the time series data, both the ADF and the KPSS tests were employed. The rationale for using both tests lies in their complementary hypotheses. The ADF test evaluates the null hypothesis that the series contains a unit root (it is non-stationary), while the KPSS test assumes stationarity as the null hypothesis. By applying both tests, the analysis gains robustness, as this dual approach allows for cross-validation of results and helps to mitigate the risk of erroneous conclusions due to the limitations of relying on a single test. As shown in Table 4, the results of the ADF and KPSS tests are consistent with theoretical expectations. The variables (EMP, MVA, IMP, LAB, SKI, GDP, EXR, FDI, INF, and GEX) exhibit a mixed order of integration, with the highest integration observed at the first-difference level, I(1). This characteristic validates the application of the ARDL approach in the subsequent analysis.

Table 4: Unit Root and Stationarity Tests Results

Variable	ADF Test (Level)	ADF Test (1st Diff.)	Order	KPSS Test (Level)	KPSS Test (1st Diff.)	Order
EMP	-1.16	-3.97**	I(1)	0.50	0.25**	I(1)
MVA	-0.90	-3.31**	I(1)	0.08**	-	I(0)
IMP	-2.32	-5.49**	I(1)	0.55	0.35**	I(1)
LAB	-0.70	-6.20**	I(1)	0.49	0.31**	I(1)
SKI	-1.99	-5.54**	I(1)	0.12**	-	I(0)
GDP	-4.38**	-	I(0)	0.07**	-	I(0)
EXR	1.89	-3.86**	I(1)	0.66	0.40**	I(1)
FDI	0.45	-3.17**	I(1)	0.30**	-	I(0)
INF	-2.46	-5.97**	I(1)	0.29**	-	I(0)
GEX	-0.67	-5.26**	I(1)	0.11**	-	I(0)

Source: Authors' Computation. ** signifies statistical significance at 5% level.

4.3. Optimal Lag Selection

Selecting the optimal lag in ARDL models is essential for accurately representing the relationships between variables while minimising the risks of autocorrelation and overfitting, which can lead to biased estimates. Based on the Akaike Information Criterion (AIC), the optimal lag structure identified is ARDL (1, 0, 0, 1, 1, 1, 1, 1, 1).

4.4. Bounds Cointegration Test

The results presented in Table 5 show that the F-statistic value of 19.07 exceeds the upper bound critical value at the 5% significance level. This leads to the rejection of the null hypothesis, indicating the presence of a long-run relationship (cointegration) among EMP, MVA, LAB, SKI, GDP, EXR, INF, FDI, and GEX in the model.

Table 5: ARDL Bounds Test Results

Test Statistic	Value	Significance level	Critical Values	
			I(0)	I(1)
F Statistic	19.07	1%	2.62	3.77
		5%	2.11	3.15
		10%	1.85	2.85

Source: Authors' Computations

4.5. Long-run and short-run analysis

The results in Table 6 reveal a statistically significant negative relationship between GEX and EMP (the dependent variable) at the 5% significance level in the long run. In the short run, EMP(-1)* (the lagged dependent variable) has a negative and statistically significant impact on itself. Additionally, negative and statistically significant effects on EMP in the short run are observed for EXR(-1), INF(-1), FDI(-1), GEX(-1), and D(GEX). The findings indicate that GEX, GEX(-1), D(GEX), and FDI(-1) deviate from the a priori theoretical expectation of a positive relationship with EMP. Conversely, EXR(-1) and INF(-1) align with the a priori expectation of a negative effect on EMP. Moreover, the results highlight a positive and significant impact of MVA**, which serves as a proxy for GVC, and D(SKI) on EMP in the short run. The positive influence of GVC in this study aligns with the findings of Uesugi and Afolayan (2022) but contrasts with those of Pahl and Timmer (2019). This discrepancy arises because Pahl and Timmer (2019) emphasise the role of productivity and efficiency in employment outcomes. While GVC enhances economic output, it does not necessarily lead to proportional employment gains. Factors such as automation and cost-cutting measures can drive jobless growth.

Table 6: Long-Run and Short-Run Estimation Results

Panel A: Long-Run Estimation				
Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
MVA	3.64	2.37	1.53	0.16
LAB	-0.06	0.52	-0.11	0.90
SKI	0.10	0.06	1.73	0.12
GDP	-0.06	0.08	-0.80	0.44
EXR	7.66	4.10	1.86	0.10
INF	-0.21	0.10	-2.11	0.07
FDI	-0.08	0.04	-1.97	0.08
GEX	-4.49	1.75	-2.55	0.03
C	-93.95	78.01	-1.20	0.26
Panel B: Short-Run Estimation				
Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
C	-23.94	14.03	-1.70	0.13
EMP(-1)*	-0.25	0.09	-2.77	0.02
MVA**	0.92	0.38	2.42	0.04
LAB**	-0.01	0.13	-0.11	0.91
SKI(-1)	0.02	0.01	1.52	0.17
GDP(-1)	-0.01	0.01	-0.91	0.38
EXR(-1)	1.95	0.76	2.55	0.03
INF(-1)	-0.05	0.01	-2.77	0.02
FDI(-1)	-0.02	0.00	-2.56	0.03
GEX(-1)	-1.14	0.24	-4.69	0.00
D(SKI)	0.05	0.01	5.42	0.00
D(GDP)	-0.00	0.01	-0.27	0.79
D(EXR)	-0.09	0.53	-0.18	0.86
D(INF)	0.00	0.01	0.27	0.79
D(FDI)	-0.00	0.00	-1.75	0.12
D(GEX)	-2.58	0.63	-4.04	0.00
R-Squared = 0.96; Prob. (F-Statistic) = 0.00; Durbin-Watson Stat = 2.04				

Source: Authors' Computations.

The Error Correction Term (ECT) is both statistically significant and negative, indicating that 25% of the short-run disequilibrium in EMP, caused by shocks from the explanatory variables, is corrected in each period over the long run. The R-squared value shows that the model accounts for 96% of the variation in EMP. In addition, the model is statistically significant overall, as evidenced by the probability of the F-statistic.

4.6. Diagnostic Tests

Table 7 presents the results of diagnostic tests, which confirm the model's robustness. The Ramsey RESET test indicates that the model is correctly specified. The LM test confirms the absence of autocorrelation, while the Breusch-Pagan-Godfrey test shows no evidence of heteroscedasticity. Furthermore, the Jarque-Bera test suggests that the residuals are normally distributed, with no significant deviation from normality.

Table 7: Diagnostic Test Results

Type of Test	Scaled Explained SS	t-Statistic	F-Statistic	Obs*R-squared	Jarque-Bera
Ramsey RESET	-	1.45 (0.19)	2.12 (0.19)	-	-
Serial Correlation	-	-	1.19 (0.31)	3.81 (0.09)	-
Heteroscedasticity	1.21 (1.00)	-	2.76 (0.08)	19.67 (0.18)	-
Normality (JB)	-	-	-	-	0.43 (0.80)

Source: Authors' Computations. The dashes (-) signify that the statistic does not apply to the specific test in question.

4.7. Robustness Check

4.7.1. Optimal Lag Selection for the Robustness Check Model

In the robustness check model, the value of intermediate goods imports (IMP) is used as an alternative measure of GVC to assess the stability and reliability of the results under different specifications. Based on the Akaike Information Criterion (AIC), the optimal lag structure for the model is identified as ARDL (1, 1, 1, 1, 1, 1, 1, 1, 0).

4.7.2. Bounds Cointegration Test for the Robustness Check Model

The results in Table 8 show that the F-statistic value of 7.76 exceeds the upper bound critical value at the 5% significance level. Consequently, the null hypothesis is rejected, indicating the presence of a long-run relationship (cointegration) among EMP, IMP, LAB, SKI, GDP, EXR, INF, FDI, and GEX in the model.

Table 8: ARDL Bounds Test Results for the Robustness Check Model

Test Statistic	Value	Significance level	Critical Values	
			I(0)	I(1)
F Statistic	7.76	1%	2.62	3.77
		5%	2.11	3.15
		10%	1.85	2.85

Source: Authors' Computations.

4.7.3. Long-Run and Short-Run Analysis for the Robustness Check Model

The long-run analysis presented in Table 9 reveals that LAB has a statistically significant negative effect on EMP, while SKI exerts a statistically significant positive effect, both at the 5% significance level. In the short run, EMP(-1)*, LAB(-1), and D(LAB) have a statistically

significant negative impact on EMP, the dependent variable. Conversely, SKI(-1) and D(SKI) display a statistically significant positive effect on EMP. These findings align with theoretical expectations: LAB, LAB(-1), and D(LAB) demonstrate the anticipated negative relationship with EMP, while SKI, SKI(-1), and D(SKI) exhibit the expected positive association. Interestingly, no significant effect of IMP (GVC) on EMP is observed in either the short or long run. This outcome aligns with the findings of Pahl and Timmer (2019), who reported no relationship between GVC and EMP. However, it contrasts with Oladapo and Rafiu (2022), who found a positive and statistically significant relationship between GVC and EMP.

Table 9: Long-Run and Short-Run Estimation Results

Panel A: Long-Run Estimation				
Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
IMP	0.12	1.30	0.09	0.92
LAB	-0.86	0.29	-2.97	0.02
SKI	0.14	0.04	3.03	0.02
GDP	0.11	0.09	1.31	0.23
EXR	2.95	2.88	1.02	0.34
INF	-0.11	0.06	-1.73	0.13
FDI	-0.03	0.02	-1.17	0.28
GEX	-2.32	1.80	-1.29	0.24
C	23.58	29.71	0.79	0.45
Panel B: Short-Run Estimation				
C	8.90	11.98	0.74	0.48
EMP(-1)*	-0.37	0.10	-3.55	0.01
IMP(-1)	0.04	0.49	0.09	0.92
LAB(-1)	-0.32	0.12	-2.62	0.03
SKI(-1)	0.05	0.01	3.58	0.01
GDP(-1)	0.04	0.03	1.40	0.20
EXR(-1)	1.11	1.04	1.07	0.32
INF(-1)	-0.04	0.02	-1.92	0.10
FDI(-1)	-0.01	0.01	-1.21	0.26
GEX**	-0.87	0.60	-1.43	0.20
D(IMP)	-0.48	0.44	-1.07	0.32
D(LAB)	-0.54	0.16	-3.37	0.01
D(SKI)	0.04	0.01	3.42	0.01
D(GDP)	0.02	0.01	1.53	0.17
D(EXR)	-0.52	0.92	-0.56	0.59
D(INF)	0.00	0.01	0.03	0.97
D(FDI)	-0.00	0.00	-0.78	0.46
ECM(-1)	-0.37	0.02	-13.92	0.00
R-Squared = 0.95; Prob (F-Statistic) = 0.00; Durbin-Watson Stat = 1.97				

Source: Authors' Computations.

The Error Correction Term (ECT) is both statistically significant and negative, indicating that 37% of the short-run disequilibrium in EMP, caused by shocks from the explanatory variables, is corrected in each period over the long run. The R-squared value demonstrates that the model accounts for 95% of the variation in EMP. Furthermore, the overall statistical significance of the model is confirmed by the probability of the F-statistic.

4.7.4. Diagnostic Tests for the Robustness Check Model

Table 10 presents the results of diagnostic tests, confirming the suitability of the model. The Ramsey RESET test indicates that the model is correctly specified. The LM test verifies the absence of autocorrelation, while the Breusch-Pagan-Godfrey test shows no evidence of heteroscedasticity. Additionally, the Jarque-Bera test confirms that the residuals are normally distributed.

Table 10: Diagnostic Test Results

Type of Test	Scaled Explained SS	t-Statistic	F-Statistic	Obs*R-squared	Jarque-Bera
Ramsey RESET	-	2.42 (0.06)	5.86 (0.06)	-	-
Serial Correlation	-	-	2.29 (0.19)	7.23 (0.07)	-
Heteroscedasticity	0.59(1.00)	-	0.58 (0.81)	14.05 (0.59)	-
Normality (JB)	-	-	-	-	1.35 (0.50)

Source: Authors' Computations. The dashes (-) signify that the statistic does not apply to the specific test in question.

4.8 Stability of Results: Main and Robustness Models

Comparison of the main model (manufacturing value-added as GVC proxy) and the robustness model (intermediate goods imports as proxy) reveals that model specification significantly influences the employment outcomes in Nigeria's manufacturing sector.

In the main model, manufacturing value-added exerts a positive and significant short-run effect on employment, supporting the view that domestic value addition enhances job creation through improved production and foreign investment. However, when GVC is proxied by intermediate goods imports, the relationship becomes insignificant, implying that import-dependent and capital-intensive processes generate limited employment.

Labour cost shows a consistent negative long-run relationship with employment in both models, reflecting structural inefficiencies and weak labour absorption, with a stronger short-run negative effect in the robustness model. By contrast, skills requirement remains positive and significant across models and time horizons, underscoring the importance of human capital development.

Macroeconomic effects vary. Exchange rate depreciation positively affects employment only in the short run in the main model, while foreign direct investment has a negative long-run effect in the main model but no significant impact in the robustness model, suggesting that employment gains depend on the nature of investments. Government expenditure is negatively related to employment in the long run in both models, pointing to possible inefficiencies in public spending. Inflation negatively affects employment only in the main model, while GDP shows no significant effect in either model, indicating that overall economic growth alone does not guarantee manufacturing job creation without targeted interventions.

5. CONCLUSION/RECOMMENDATIONS

This study examined Global Value Chain participation and employment creation in Nigeria's manufacturing sector, using alternative Global Value Chain measures. The main model, proxied by manufacturing value-added, reveals a positive and significant short-run effect on employment, consistent with a priori expectations and Global Value Chain theory, implying that domestic value addition promotes job creation through improved production and foreign investment attraction. In contrast, the robustness model, based on intermediate goods imports,

shows no significant employment effect, suggesting that import-dependent and capital-intensive processes generate limited jobs.

Labour cost exhibits a consistent negative long-run relationship with employment across both models, reflecting structural inefficiencies and weak labour absorption. Conversely, skills requirement remains positive and significant across models and periods, supporting Human Capital theory and highlighting the importance of workforce capabilities. Exchange rate depreciation stimulates employment only in the short run in the main model, while foreign direct investment shows a negative long-run effect in the main model and no significant effect in the robustness model. Government expenditure negatively affects long-run employment, indicating inefficiencies or crowding-out effects, while the inconsistent roles of inflation and GDP suggest that macroeconomic stability alone cannot drive manufacturing employment without targeted policies. Overall, employment gains from GVC participation depend largely on domestic value addition and skill intensity rather than reliance on intermediate imports.

Based on the findings, this study recommends that first, government should implement industrial policies that promote local production, support SMEs, and improve infrastructure to deepen domestic value addition and employment. Secondly, labour market reforms should enhance employment matching, strengthen industry–academia collaboration, and prioritize vocational training and skill acquisition aligned with manufacturing needs. Thirdly, fiscal policy should prioritise productive investments (e.g., industrial parks and technology hubs), reduce bureaucratic constraints, and incentivise labour-intensive industries through coordinated public–private initiatives. Fourthly, trade policy should encourage domestic production of intermediate goods through targeted tax incentives or subsidies to strengthen backward linkages and sustainable job creation.

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